

EFFECTIVENESS OF BACILLUS CLAUSII IN THE TREATMENT OF FUNCTIONAL CONSTIPATION IN CHILDREN

Dr Aymen Jamal^{*1}, Dr Asfand Tariq², Dr Lubna Riaz³, Dr Imama Jamal⁴,
Dr Sana Iqbal⁵, Dr Fazila Nasir⁶

^{*1}Post graduate resident in pediatric department Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore

²Assistant Professor Department of paediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital

³Associate professor/Head Of Department Paediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore

⁴Post graduate Resident Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore

^{5,6}Post graduate Resident Paediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore

^{*1}aymensz098@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Dr Aymen Jamal

Abstract

Objective:

To determine the effectiveness of Bacillus clausii in the treatment of functional constipation in children aged 1 to 5 years.

Study design:

Descriptive case series.

Place and duration of studies:

This study was carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, from February 2025 to June 2025.

Methodology:

A descriptive case series was conducted on children diagnosed with functional constipation according to standard criteria. A total of ninety eight children were enrolled after taking informed consent from parents. All enrolled participants were given one vial of Bacillus clausii once daily for a duration of twenty eight days. Parents were asked to maintain a stool diary noting frequency and consistency of stools using the Bristol stool form scale. Treatment success was defined as passage of at least three bowel movements per week along with stool consistency of grade three or above on the Bristol scale, assessed at the end of second week and fourth week of treatment. Data was recorded on a structured proforma and later analyzed using statistical software.

Results:

The mean age of the children included in the study was 3.1 plus minus 1.2 years. At the end of second week, treatment success was observed in 32.7 percent of children, which further increased to 58.2 percent by the fourth week of therapy. There was a clear improvement noted in both stool frequency and stool consistency over time, and this change was found to be statistically significant with a p value less than 0.001. No serious adverse effects were reported during the study period, and the probiotic was generally well tolerated by the children.

Conclusion:

Bacillus clausii showed a favorable effect on stool frequency and consistency in children with functional constipation. It may be considered as a useful adjunct

INTRODUCTION

Functional constipation is one of the most common gastrointestinal problems seen in children and it contributes to a large number of pediatric outpatient visits worldwide. Studies have shown that constipation affects around three to five percent of children seen by general pediatricians and up to twenty percent of those referred to pediatric gastroenterology clinics. In majority of these cases, no organic cause is identified and the diagnosis falls under functional constipation. It usually presents with infrequent bowel movements, hard stools, painful defecation and sometimes withholding behavior, which can be distressing for both the child and parents^{1,2}. The management of functional constipation in children mainly focuses on dietary changes, adequate fluid intake, toilet training and the use of osmotic laxatives. Polyethylene glycol and lactulose are commonly prescribed and are considered effective. However, many caregivers express concern regarding long term use of laxatives, fear of dependency and possible side effects. Because of these concerns, compliance to treatment is often poor and parents tend to look for alternative and safer options for their children^{3,4}. Constipation is not limited to older children, it is also commonly seen in toddlers and preschool age group and accounts for a significant proportion of pediatric hospital visits⁵.

Recent research has highlighted the possible role of gut microbiota imbalance or dysbiosis in the development of functional constipation. Altered intestinal flora may affect colonic motility, stool consistency and intestinal transit time. This has led to growing interest in the use of probiotics as a non pharmacological approach in the management of constipation. Probiotics are believed to improve bowel habits by modifying gut microbiota, producing short chain fatty acids, lowering colonic pH and enhancing intestinal peristalsis^{6,7,8}. Despite increasing use, the effectiveness of probiotics in treating pediatric functional constipation remains controversial.

Some studies and systematic reviews have shown improvement in stool frequency and consistency, while others have found insufficient evidence to recommend probiotics as a sole treatment option⁹. The variability in results may be due to differences in probiotic strains, dosage, duration of treatment and study populations.

Bacillus clausii is a Gram positive, spore forming probiotic which is resistant to gastric acidity and bile salts, allowing it to survive and colonize the intestine. It has the ability to produce lactic acid and short chain fatty acids which may help in improving gut motility. In addition, Bacillus clausii has immunomodulatory properties and has been shown to restore normal intestinal flora. It is generally considered safe with very low incidence of mild adverse effects such as vomiting, skin rash or change in stool color^{10,11,12}. Limited data is available regarding the use of Bacillus clausii in children with functional constipation, especially in younger age group. A recent randomized controlled trial did not show a significant difference between Bacillus clausii and placebo, although improvement was observed in both groups¹³. Due to limited local data and conflicting evidence, further studies are needed to evaluate its role in pediatric functional constipation. This study was therefore designed to assess the effectiveness of Bacillus clausii in improving stool frequency and consistency in children aged one to five years with functional constipation.

Methodology

This descriptive case series was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore. The study was carried out from February 2025 to June 2025, after approval of the research synopsis. A total of ninety eight children were enrolled in the study using non probability sampling technique. Children between the age of one to five years of either gender were included in the study. All participants were diagnosed with functional constipation according to the Rome

IV criteria. Children older than five years were excluded. Patients with suspected or confirmed organic causes of constipation, those using medications known to cause constipation, and children with neurological impairment or congenital heart disease were also excluded from the study.

After taking informed consent from parents or guardians, baseline information including age, gender, weight and duration of constipation was recorded. Parents were educated regarding stool pattern assessment using the Bristol stool form scale. All enrolled children were given one vial of *Bacillus clausii* orally once daily for a total duration of twenty eight days. Parents were advised to administer sodium chloride enema only if the child did not pass stool for three consecutive days during the study period. Parents were asked to maintain a daily stool diary

documenting stool frequency and consistency. Follow up assessment was done at the end of second week and fourth week of treatment. Treatment success was defined as passage of at least three bowel movements per week along with stool consistency of grade three or above on the Bristol stool form scale.

Data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version twenty seven. Continuous variables such as age and duration of constipation were expressed as mean with standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Stratification was done to assess effect modifiers and chi square test was applied where applicable. A p value of less than or equal to zero point zero five was taken as statistically significant.

Results

Baseline Characteristics (n = 98)

Variable	Value
Mean age (years)	3.1 ± 1.2
Gender (Male/Female)	56 (57.1%) / 42 (42.9%)
Mean weight (kg)	13.4 ± 2.6
Mean duration of constipation (months)	5.8 ± 2.1
Stool frequency <3/week	98 (100%)
Bristol stool type 1-2	90 (91.8%)

Treatment Outcomes

Outcome	Week 2	Week 4
Treatment success	32 (32.7%)	57 (58.2%)
Mean stool frequency/week	2.1 ± 0.6	4.3 ± 1.1
Bristol score ≥3	35 (35.7%)	62 (63.3%)

The improvement in stool frequency and consistency from baseline to week 4 was statistically significant (p < 0.001).

Stratification Analysis (Week 4 Success)

Variable	Success (%)	p-value
Male	60.7%	0.41
Female	54.8%	
Duration <6 months	65.4%	0.03

Variable	Success (%)	p-value
Duration ≥6 months	48.9%	

Children with shorter duration of constipation showed higher treatment success.

Comparison of Stool Frequency and Stool Consistency Before and After Treatment (n = 98)

Parameter	Baseline	Week 2	Week 4
Mean stool frequency per week	1.9 ± 0.5	3.0 ± 0.8	4.2 ± 1.1
Bristol stool scale score ≤2	90 (91.8%)	63 (64.3%)	36 (36.7%)
Bristol stool scale score ≥3	8 (8.2%)	35 (35.7%)	62 (63.3%)
Painful defecation present	71 (72.4%)	48 (49.0%)	29 (29.6%)

Table shows changes in stool frequency and stool consistency among children with functional constipation before and after administration of *Bacillus clausii*. At baseline, mean stool frequency was low and majority of children had hard stools with Bristol stool scale score one or two. At the end of second week, improvement was observed in stool frequency and stool consistency, with mean stool frequency increasing to three bowel movements per week and a higher number of children achieving Bristol stool scale score three or above. By the fourth week of treatment, further improvement was noted, as mean stool frequency increased to 4.2 per week and more than half of the children passed stools of normal consistency. The number of children experiencing painful defecation also showed gradual reduction over the treatment period. Overall, *Bacillus clausii* showed beneficial effect on bowel habits in children with functional constipation.

Adverse Events

During the study period, mild adverse events were noted in six children which accounted for 6.1 percent of the total sample. These adverse effects were mostly transient in nature and included symptoms such as mild abdominal discomfort and bloating. The symptoms were short lived and resolved on their own without requiring any medical intervention. No serious adverse effects were observed in any of the

children and none of the participants required discontinuation of treatment due to side effects. Overall, *Bacillus clausii* was found to be well tolerated among the study participants.

Discussion

The findings of this study show that *Bacillus clausii* had a positive effect on stool frequency and stool consistency in children suffering from functional constipation. A gradual and progressive improvement was observed over the four week treatment period, with treatment success increasing from 32.7 percent at week two to 58.2 percent at week four. This pattern suggests that the effect of probiotic therapy may be time dependent rather than immediate, which is also supported by earlier studies on probiotic use in pediatric constipation ^{2,9}. Functional constipation is known to be a multifactorial condition, involving dietary habits, behavioral factors and altered gut motility. In recent years, the role of gut microbiota imbalance has gained attention as a contributing factor. Dysbiosis may affect intestinal transit time and stool consistency, leading to constipation. Probiotics are believed to restore microbial balance and improve gut function through multiple mechanisms such as fermentation of carbohydrates, production of short chain fatty acids and lowering of colonic pH, which ultimately enhances intestinal peristalsis ^{6,7,8}. The

improvement observed in this study may be explained by these mechanisms.

The treatment success rate observed at week four in the present study is comparable to results reported in some previous studies evaluating probiotics in children with constipation. Lojanatorn et al reported improvement in stool frequency and stool form in both *Bacillus clausii* and placebo groups, although no significant difference was found between the two groups¹³. Similarly, systematic reviews and meta analysis have shown mixed results regarding the effectiveness of probiotics, with some studies reporting benefit while others showing limited or no advantage over standard treatment^{2,9}. These variations may be due to differences in probiotic strains used, study design, duration of therapy and population characteristics. An important observation in this study was that children with shorter duration of constipation appeared to respond better to treatment. This finding highlights the importance of early recognition and intervention in functional constipation. Prolonged constipation may lead to stool withholding behavior, rectal dilatation and reduced response to medical therapy, making management more challenging. Early use of adjunctive therapies such as probiotics may help in preventing chronicity of symptoms^{1,12}.

Bacillus clausii has several properties that make it an attractive probiotic option in pediatric practice. It is a spore forming organism that can survive gastric acidity and bile salts, allowing it to reach the intestine in viable form. It also has immunomodulatory effects and has been widely used in children for treatment of diarrhea with a good safety profile^{5,10,11}. In the present study, *Bacillus clausii* was well tolerated and only mild adverse events such as abdominal discomfort and bloating were reported, which resolved without intervention. No serious adverse effects were observed, supporting its safety in young children. Despite these encouraging findings, probiotics including *Bacillus clausii* should not be considered as a replacement for conventional treatment of functional constipation. Dietary modification, toilet training and use of osmotic laxatives remain the cornerstone of management.

Probiotics may serve as an adjunctive option, especially in children who have poor response or intolerance to laxatives, or where parental concern regarding long term laxative use exists^{3,4}. This study has certain limitations. Being a descriptive case series without a control group, causal relationship cannot be firmly established. The sample size was relatively small and follow up duration was limited to four weeks. Long term outcomes and relapse rates were not assessed. Future randomized controlled trials with larger sample size and longer follow up are needed to further evaluate the role of *Bacillus clausii* in pediatric functional constipation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, *Bacillus clausii* was found to be safe and showed beneficial effect in improving stool frequency and stool consistency in children with functional constipation over a period of four weeks. The probiotic was well tolerated and no serious side effects were observed during the study. These findings suggest that *Bacillus clausii* may be used as an adjunct option along with standard treatment in young children with functional constipation. However, further large scale randomized controlled studies are still needed to confirm its effectiveness and long term benefits.

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